
PERSONALITY-ORIENTED APPROACH AS A KEY FACTOR IN MODERN EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING

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Shohsanam Yunusovna Tohirova

tokhirovashohsanam9420@gmail.com

Teacher at Foreign Languages Department

Karshi Engineering Economics Institute

Abstract.

The person-centered approach is aimed at humanizing the educational process and is designed to directly reveal the potential abilities and capabilities of students, to establish the principles of mutual respect and communication skills. The article discusses the main aspects of the personality-oriented approach as a key factor in modern education and upbringing.

Keywords.

personality-oriented approach, modern education, student-centered learning, intellectual development

Introduction:

The traditional system of education and upbringing, which was based on the differentiation of knowledge, authoritarianism, a culture of usefulness, is becoming outdated, giving way to a personality-oriented system of education and upbringing, which is based on humanism, integration of knowledge, dialogism and a culture of dignity. That is, the traditional understanding of the essence and significance of education as an opportunity to acquire knowledge, skills, and prepare a person for life has been replaced by a view of education as the formation of a person, finding himself, his human image, revealing a unique individuality, spirituality, and creative potential. The idea of a student-centered approach in education is not new.

Literature review:

To one degree or another, it is used in all didactic systems: "interest" in I.F. Herbart, K.D. Ushinsky, P.F. Kapterev reflect a long-standing, empirically established view of teachers about learning as an activity, as the realization of certain life aspirations of the individual. Orientation to the personality of the student, understanding the impossibility of achieving educational goals without

his/her participation acted as a non-verbalized, clearly unconscious norm of pedagogical activity, and long before fundamental studies of the role of the personality factor in learning were carried out.

The focus of personality-oriented education is a person who strives for the maximum realization of his capabilities (self-actualization), is open to the perception of new experience, and is capable of making a conscious choice in various situations. It is the achievement of such qualities by a person that is proclaimed the main goal of education, in contrast to the formalized transfer of knowledge and social norms to the student in traditional technology. The peculiarity of the paradigm of the goals of personality-oriented technologies lies in the orientation on the properties of the personality, its formation, its development not by someone else's order, but in accordance with natural abilities. According to A.A. Munkueva, the conceptual content of the term "personally oriented education" has not yet been fully defined, it is interpreted and understood in different ways. Assessing the situation in modern education, the researcher believes that the desire for innovation, encountering the lack of a clear idea of their methods and content, sometimes gives rise to a skeptical attitude towards innovation in general [19].

Discussions:

Personality-oriented learning is considered as a certain way designed organization of the learning process that creates conditions for the development of students' ability to self-education, self-development, self-determination, independence and self-realization; allowing to more fully manifest and realize his capabilities in accordance with his training, abilities and psycho-physiological characteristics. This implies the position on the essence of student-centered learning as an activity that protects the student, preserves, transmits and develops culture, creates creative environments for the development of the student, stimulates his individual and collective creativity.

Therefore, student-centered learning is aimed, firstly, not only at achieving the planned results by each student, but also at creating all the necessary conditions for this. Secondly, to identify and develop the personal qualities of students, their thinking, cognitive abilities, skills for self-acquisition of knowledge in order to qualitatively prepare students for future professional and social life.

When designing a personality-oriented education system, it is necessary:

- to determine the design goal - the development of the student's creative individuality;

- determination of the means that ensure the realization of the set goal, as pedagogical conditions that take into account the needs, interests and individual characteristics of students:

- the search for the unity of the vertical and horizontal lines of the student's development (changing the student through activity and attitude towards it) and a corresponding change in the evaluation criteria.

The implementation of personality-oriented education requires the development of such content of education, which includes not only scientific knowledge, but also ways of organizing it, the search for internal integration, which allows to overcome the disunity of curricula, subjects and extracurricular activities and is capable of leading to a holistic vision of the world and oneself in it, and also metaknowledge, i.e. techniques and methods of cognition. The main criterion for evaluating an educational program in this system is its ability to maximize the potential and stimulate the creative abilities of students; compliance with regulations; taking into account the real conditions of the socio-cultural environment; manufacturability non-creative approach; integrity and systems approach.

The main principles of personality-oriented education A.A. Munkueva names the following: conformity to nature - taking into account the individual, age and psychological characteristics of students; variability and cultural conformity; activity and independence; development and systems approach; reliance on the subjective experience of the student, his/her interests and needs of freedom: freedom of choice and responsibility for his choice; the principle "The whole is as the interconnection of parts"; the principle of Love, which is the basis of deep spiritual communication; principles of pluralism, equality, dialogism²⁹⁴.

The study of this problem allows the teachers to single out at least three positions in a student-centered approach to education:

The first position considers the student as a subject of cognition and proposes to build training based on the student's cognitive experience, his abilities and interests, giving him/her the opportunity to realize him/herself in cognition, in learning activities and in learning behavior. Moreover, for this it is necessary to teach him/her ways of thinking and learning activities, thereby ensuring his/her intellectual development [22,306].

The second position considers the student as a subject of life activity, proposes to build learning on the basis of the student's life experience (not only the

²⁹⁴ Munkueva A.A. Pedagogical conditions of individually oriented education/ A.A. Munkueva. Ulan-Ude, 2000

experience of learning, but also communication, productive activity, creativity, etc.) in such a way that he/she can become not only the subject of his educational activity, but also all his life - present and future. To do this, it is necessary to ensure, in addition to intellectual development, personal growth, developing the ability for strategic activity, creativity, criticality, meaning creation, a system of needs and motives, the ability to self-determination, self-development, a positive self-concept and more.

The third position is close to the second in a broad understanding of the subjectivity of the student, but, it sees the possibility of developing subjectivity not only in learning, but also in a student-oriented holistic pedagogical process; secondly, he insists not only on natural conformity (following the specifics of specific age periods), but also on the cultural conformity of the pedagogical process - the child develops not only as a subject of knowledge, a subject of life, but also as a subject of culture - its bearer, keeper, user, creator. The third position is closest to us as it most fully and harmoniously reflects the ideas of a personality-oriented education of a holistic human personality, especially since it does not cross out, but naturally includes and raises the first two to a new level. At the same time, these positions can be considered as stages in the development of the idea of personality-oriented education. A university teacher who begins to implement these ideas can either go through the consistent development and implementation of each position in their activities, or immediately begin to build a holistic personality-oriented process.

Conclusion:

Thus, we can conclude that student-centered education sets the following tasks for itself and teachers: to ensure 1) personal growth, development of subjectivity, self-development of the student; 2) his intellectual development; 3) the formation in his mind of a holistic picture of the world. The following provisions can be identified as the most important provisions of the theory of student-centered education: - the personality of the student is put forward at the center of the proposed theoretical model of student-centered education, and the emphasis is shifted to help in the formation and development of his personal qualities, to assist in the disclosure and the manifestation of the intellectual potential of the student, and not the forcible formation of a personality with predetermined properties that meet the requirements of society; - centering on the personality is called upon to realize the personal aspirations of the individual by means of education, to help its self-realization; develop the ability to solve new or ill-defined problems; to form thinking skills of a higher order; to promote the development of creative, rather

than productive knowledge among students; - the personal orientation of education is based on the subjective activity of the student, who not only learns independently, but also develops his personal qualities.

Personally oriented education should be aimed at developing the above-mentioned qualities of a self-actualizing personality in students; training is focused on the development of cognitive activity and equipping students with methods of independent discoveries; - personal orientation involves the creation of conditions to meet the needs of students in communication, research, creativity, creation, i.e.

Development of social and communicative abilities of the individual. The purpose of student-centered learning is to create such conditions for educational interaction between the student and the teacher, when each person is treated as the highest independent value; the content, forms, methods and means of teaching ensure the effective development of the student's individuality; contribute to the formation of such personal qualities as the ability to self-education, self-education, self-education, self-development, the formation of creative abilities, cognitive interest, diligence, the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice; take into account the individual characteristics of the student and the preferred ways of working with educational material [53,130]. The humanistic paradigm of personality-oriented education is characterized by the fact that personality-oriented education goes through several stages, as it involves the formation of the student's personality, finding himself, his image: unique individuality, spirituality, creativity. The implementation of the personal-human approach in education assumes the recognition of the personal meaning and personal significance of learning in each child. The acquisition of personal meaning is helped by the content of personality-oriented education, which includes the following mandatory components: cognitive, activity-creative and personal.

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